

A Proposed Protocol for Measuring the Effectiveness of EUC Education

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Abstract

Learning methods for software such as Excel are still under development. Education designed to keep pace with rapidly evolving software must be updated each time the software changes.

There is no final form for such educational methods. Since there is no guarantee that personal computers or operating systems—let alone application software—will retain their current form in the future, even principles that appear universal may eventually be overturned. What matters is building a measurement system capable of adapting to change.

To date, instruction in software such as Excel has been delivered by individual educators, each adapting their own approach to address gaps in learning outcomes.

Yet the fundamental methodology of software education has not changed in more than thirty years since personal computer training first emerged.

In the case of Excel, instruction typically follows a fixed sequence: what Excel is, screen orientation, entering values, entering formulas, copying formulas, and applying formatting. Through this sequence, learners are expected to develop an experiential understanding of Excel.

The problem is that instructors cannot judge, in the moment, whether a learner has genuinely grasped what Excel is or has merely learned a sequence of operations.

When an instructor asks “Do you understand?” there is no way to tell, without extending the session considerably, whether the learner understood the operation or understood the principle. Given the practical constraints of training delivery, that is not realistic.

As a result, learners acquire only procedural knowledge and are unable to handle the novel situations they constantly encounter in the workplace (Sato, 2026).

For this reason, end-user computing (EUC) education is in constant need of reform.

Whether the current educational framework is sound has gone unmeasured for more than thirty years, even if it may have been assessed at the outset.

Prior research on EUC training effectiveness—including Elrod et al. (2015)—has measured skill acquisition through operation-level tests that assess whether learners can replicate demonstrated procedures. However, such tests conflate procedural

memory with principled understanding. This protocol addresses that gap by measuring transfer: whether learners can apply an underlying principle to a function they have not been explicitly taught.

This paper therefore proposes a methodology for conducting such measurement on a regular basis.

Method

In accordance with principles of informed consent, educators applying this protocol should explain the process to participants and obtain their agreement in advance.

The first step is to teach a single principle that generalizes across the domain. In the case of Excel functions, if teaching the VLOOKUP function can lay the groundwork for understanding any other function, the instruction should cover: the principle behind VLOOKUP, why VLOOKUP is appropriate in a given context, how learners can identify the function name on their own, and how to work through an unfamiliar function for the first time. This may be delivered as explanation alone or combined with hands-on practice.

See Appendix A for a detailed protocol example.

The second step is to measure whether the principle has taken root by presenting a related but untaught problem—for example, a task involving HLOOKUP or XLOOKUP—with limited hints, and asking learners to submit their work.

See Appendix B for sample assessment problems.

The educator uses the submitted answers to assess whether the instructional approach is effective, then scores the work and returns the results along with explanations to the participants. This is the ethically preferred practice in a research context.

This process may be automated, or, if the educator retains copies of the answers, self-scoring by learners is also acceptable.

This approach allows the effectiveness of the instructional format to be quantified as a score.

Educators should evaluate three criteria: 1) whether the function name is correct; 2) whether the function is used correctly, including absolute references where required; and 3) whether the result is correct. Each criterion is worth one point, for a maximum of three points per problem.

Evaluation Score = Total Score ÷ (Number of Problems × 3) [%]

This allows an assessment of how reliably the method works, even if not perfectly. A benchmark of approximately 90% or above is a reasonable threshold.

If nine out of ten learners grasp the material, the remaining one in ten can realistically receive individual support. The appropriate threshold will depend on the educator's capacity for individual instruction. For example, if an educator can support only five learners individually and the total cohort is one hundred, the threshold rises to 95% or above.

Ownership of Outcomes

It is desirable for the outcomes of this work to be shared with the public as common knowledge. However, since designing specific assessment tasks involves intellectual effort, the resulting work may properly belong to the individual educator who created it.

Definition of Misuse

This method contains a structural risk of drawing participants into an asymmetric commercial relationship. Under the guise of a free Excel session and skills assessment, the feedback process could be used to recruit participants into paid courses offered by the educator.

This protocol strongly condemns any such solicitation directed at participants, and defines such conduct as misuse.

References

Sato, Y. (2026). 「できない」の構造的欺瞞と教育市場の病理 [The structural deception of “cannot do” and the pathology of the education market]. <https://doi.org/10.51094/jxiv.3587>

Elrod, H., Pittman, K., Norris, J., & Tiggeman, T. (2015). Excel training and the technology student learning outcome. *Academy of Educational Leadership Journal*, 19(2), 43–49.

Appendix A: Sample Teaching Protocol Using the VLOOKUP Function

In Excel, information that cannot be found in one table is often linked to another. Suppose Table A contains only the sales date and a product code number. In this state, we cannot tell what was sold or at what price. Table B, however, contains the product name and unit price corresponding to each code. By matching the product code in Table A against the product code in Table B, we can identify the product name and unit price. In other words, if Table A contains a product code, the product name and price are meaning embedded within that code.

The VLOOKUP function is what retrieves that embedded meaning. “V” stands for vertical—it indicates that the lookup table is arranged vertically. “LOOKUP” means to find a value and return it. As this example shows, function names can often be inferred from the English words they combine.

Next, we will look at two ways to enter this function. Either approach is fine—use whichever feels more natural.

Method 1: Typing the function directly

Let’s find the product name in Table A by typing the formula directly. In the cell to the right of Table A, type “=” followed by the first few letters of the function name. A list of

matching functions will appear, and you can select VLOOKUP from the list.

Once you have selected the function name, you need to enter its arguments. A tooltip will pop up with hints—use that as your guide. The tooltip shows four arguments: lookup value, table array, column index number, and range lookup. Think about what each of these means as you fill them in.

What is the lookup value? It is the value in the current row that you want to look up—in this case, the product code in Table A. Type a comma to separate arguments (commas separate arguments when typing directly). The table array is the reference table—Table B. The column index number refers to which column within the table array you want to return; here, you want the second column, so enter 2. After the next comma, you will be prompted to choose between exact match and approximate match. Since you want an exact match, select that option. Once all arguments are entered, close the parenthesis, review the formula to confirm it is correct, press Enter to confirm, and verify that the result is as expected. That completes the direct-entry method.

Method 2: Using the fx button

Now let's find the unit price in Table A using the fx button. Click the fx button. The Function Wizard dialog will open.

You can search for functions here. Type VLOOKUP in the search box and click Search, then select VLOOKUP from the results. Note that this search box also accepts plain-language descriptions such as "sum" rather than the exact function name.

The dialog displays a description of the function and a separate input field for each argument. Clicking on an input field shows a hint for that argument at the bottom of the dialog. Use these hints to guide your entries.

When using the Function Wizard, you do not need to type commas between arguments.

Once all arguments are entered, verify that they are correct. At this point, the dialog already shows a preview of the result—check that it matches what you expected. If everything looks right, click OK, then confirm that the result appears correctly in the cell.

Appendix B: Sample Assessment Problems

Problem 1: Tests procedural application with the function name provided

1. VLOOKUP can only search when the lookup value appears in the leftmost column of the reference table. XLOOKUP removes this restriction. Using the XLOOKUP function, look up the product category for each product name in Table C by referencing Table D. Specify only the first three arguments and omit the fourth onward.

Problem 2: Tests the ability to identify the appropriate function

2. Find the reward points corresponding to each purchase amount in Table E by referencing Table F, which is arranged horizontally. Retrieve the points for the closest matching purchase amount.

Note: The content of the data tables used is not prescribed. The essence of measurement lies in whether learners can transfer the underlying principle to a function they have not been explicitly taught.